

8T – High Energy Spaces & Probability of Life over Infinite Dimensional Universe Packet

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Abstract:

By analyzing the features of the multiverse as presented of in the 8T thesis, the author analysis the space which was mapped into energy, i.e. the Ricci flow space. this space is different with many respects, it is flat, time invariant and serve as the kernel between two manifolds. it is in fact the same between each manifold pair.

This space must be accessible at extremum energies. In addition, the author analyzes the probability of life given at least some of the manifold arbitrary variation distributions are identical.

Introduction

The main equation of the 8T is describing the variation of a Lorentz manifold, which according to the second equation (1.1) can be expressed as being part of a manifold packet. Such a theoretical construction manifested in one equation, is able to provide an answer to three major questions at the heart of major cosmology. The flatness puzzle, the "dark energy" puzzle and the "dark matter" puzzle by (1.2).

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_m - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_n = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The question in which the author will try to answer is the following: what are the full implications of the Ricci curvature term, $\partial g / \partial t$. In the 8T it stands in two different contexts. The first is the usual Ricci curvature, which in discrete amounts is isomorphic for Bosons. The second and the one which is the more mysterious is that the term $\partial g / \partial t$ stands for a space in it itself. That is because of two reasons, the first is the arrow correlated to that term in the 8T. The second is the condition $\partial g / \partial t = 0$. The arrow that presented was:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi: g &\longrightarrow E \\ E &= \hat{H} \end{aligned}$$

That arrow than resulting in a term that is energy to time in the main equation. In addition, such a term is separated in a sense, as none of us ever witnesses raw energy varying over time. The second reason was the condition, $\partial E / \partial t = 0$ which is needed for explaining the phenomena of outward acceleration from extremum curvatures. If the 8T is describing manifolds which interact with each other, in particular flattening each other, and yet as residents of one manifold, we have not seen the flattening universe. That is indicating they are separated by some way, which serve as the role for that space, which, if one intuition is correct, serve as a common gate for both manifolds.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} \delta g_m - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} \delta g_n = 0$$

$$1 \leq m, n < k/2$$

$$\frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} = \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} = 0 ;$$

It makes sense to consider that space as a space which accessible at extremum energy. Such space has a feature of partially time invariant, and as far as one can see, it is the space in between two distinct manifolds interacting via extremum curvatures. That can be explain as the areas of extremum curvature interact with each other, they create a repulsion which is synonymous with energy, that energy direction is away from that extremum curvatures, leading to the flattening and the acceleration from them areas. The following can be explained in another manner. If there was not a separating space, there will not be a finite dimensional manifolds, i.e. universe, but infinite dimensional. Another possible way to analyze is to ignore all the terms in the main equation other than the last two.

$$\frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} - \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} = 0$$

Those manifolds has areas of extremum curvature but with opposite orientation, leading to manifestation of total energy. Since all manifold pair in the packet share the same relation, that is same as stating $k \rightarrow \infty$ or:

$$\left(\frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} - \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} = 0 \right) \forall s_\omega$$

$$s_\omega = s_m + s_n$$

The number of this space projections is half of the number manifolds in the packet. This space must be manifested as flat, time invariant partially and accessible at extremum energies.

Since it is the same for all, imagine that a race reached an extremum energy of the matrix:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}_m}{\partial \mathbf{t}_m} = 0$$

Since:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{g}_m}{\partial \mathbf{t}_m} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}_n}{\partial \mathbf{t}_n}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial \mathbf{g}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}_n}{\partial \mathbf{t}_n} \delta \mathbf{g}_n$$

By lowering the energy, it now can access complimentary manifold. The same applies endlessly over the packet. The term $\partial \mathbf{g} / \partial \mathbf{t}$ serve as the kernel of distinct manifolds and the key space allowing to jumping, by requiring $\partial \mathbf{g} / \partial \mathbf{t} = 0$ it turns to the Kernel of those two manifolds. another point that one would analyze is the probability of life. We have assumed that those manifolds has the same curvature areas with different arbitrary variations distributions which vanish into matter. when the latter summed across the area of extremum curvature it is equalized among the two manifolds.

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_1} \in [0,1]$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_2} \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{s_1} \neq \mathcal{R}^{s_2}$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \delta g_i \equiv \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \delta g_i$$

Suppose for the sake of the argument that the distribution in at least part of the manifolds in the infinite packet is identical, that there exist a subset of universes in which there is alignment of stars which due to their size can be considered life-harboring, i.e. earth-like diameter, water containing and at the right distance from a light emitting star. Than at each distinct star harboring life, there exit some chance that exit life in at least some distinct manifold distribution on the packet. Take the infinite manifolds of the packet and the probability will aspire one. Of course that is no indication life would form as it is on earth. The chain of accidents would be most likely very different; the stages of life would be very likely different as well. To put that in rigor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^z \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{zk} \in \mathcal{R}^z; z, k \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^L \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{Lp} \in \mathcal{R}^L; L, n \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{zk} \equiv \mathcal{R}^{Lp} \rightarrow \sum_{\mathcal{A}=1}^{\mathbb{E}} [0,1]_{\mathcal{A}};$$

$$z = L;$$

$$k = p;$$

$$\left(\sum_{m=1}^{\frac{K}{2}} \delta g_i \equiv \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{K}{2}} \delta g_i \right) \cap (\mathcal{R}^{zk} \equiv \mathcal{R}^{Lp})$$

$$P_{(life)} \rightarrow 1$$

That is there exist a finite subset of distributions of size \mathbb{E} that are identical in **size** and in **distribution** in the packet, meaning matter wise. That is synonymous with stating that there is a succession of life harboring starts aligned on infinite dimensional space, which is composed by finite dimensional manifolds interacting via extremum curvatures, flattening each other. For matching it to the complexity of reality, we can state that at least part of the overall arbitrary variations distribution is identical; in particular, for the purpose of the paper, the areas that represent star harboring life.

If there is in fact a valid case to claims of distinct life forms observed in space near our earth, it would be more reasonable to assume that they would come from very close rather than a very far. That is, to assume they come from another finite dimensional manifold flattening our own, rather than a distinct galaxy in our own manifold, as the distance would be too great to travel even at the speed of light. There is no indication for exceeding the speed of light is possible, in agreement with Einstein theory of private relativity, which regard the latter as the upper limit, and the Michelson Morley experiments of the C invariance. But how large is the subset of identical variation distributions \mathbb{E} ? In other words, how many life-harboring planets aligned on the roughly same coordinate over the packet, it is most likely will never be answered, but can be estimated as a fraction of infinity. It could be several hundred life-harboring planets or several billions, just at our aligned at our own point. This would apply to each life harboring planet on this manifold.8T would indicate that there should be a celebration of life in space.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8T – The Grand Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad's Theory